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Farkhodova Shahzoda UmidkiziScientific researcher of Samarkand state
institute of foreign languages**THE PRINCIPLE OF POLITENESS IN SPEECH ADAPTATION** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13235787>**ABSTRACT**

This article shows the attitude of the speaker to the listener in the implementation of politeness strategy in English and Uzbek languages. Also, issues such as the fact that the theory of politeness is mainly focused on the analysis of the process of direct oral communication, and that one of the important reasons why speakers seek to indirectly express the pragmatic goal in speech communication is to follow the rules of politeness.

Key words: speech act, dialogic speech, pragmatic analysis, politeness principle, communication culture.

Farhodova Shaxzoda Umidqizi

Samarqand davlat chet tillat instituti mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

NUTQIY MOSLASHUVDA XUSHMUOMILALIK TAMOYILI**ANNOTATSIYA**

Mazkur maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarida xushmuomilalik strategiyasi voqelanishida so'zlovchining tinglovchiga bo'lgan munosabati namoyon qilingan. Shuningdek, xushmuomilalik nazariyasi asosan bevosita og'zaki muloqot jarayonini tahlil qilishga yo'naltirilganligi, nutqiy muloqotda so'zlovchilarning pragmatik mo'ljalni bilvosita ifodalashga intilishlarining muhim sabablaridan biri xushmuomilalik qoidalariga amal qilishi kabi masalalari ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: nutqiy akt, dialogik nutq, pragmatik tahlil, xushmuomilalik tamoyili, muloqot madaniyati.

Фарходова Шахзода УмидкизиНаучный соискатель Самаркандского государственного
института иностранных языков**ПРИНЦИП ВЕЖЛИВОСТИ В ПРИСПОСОБЛЕНИЕ РЕЧИ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

В данной статье показано отношение говорящего к слушающему при реализации стратегии вежливости в английском и узбекском языках. Также рассматриваются такие вопросы, как тот факт, что теория вежливости ориентирована в основном на анализ процесса

непосредственного устного общения и что одной из важных причин, по которой говорящие стремятся косвенно выразить прагматическую цель в речевом общении, является следование правилам вежливости.

Ключевые слова: речевой акт, диалогическая речь, прагматический анализ, принцип вежливости, культура общения.

Introduction

Issues related to the discourse structure, components, substantive features, and pragma-discursive nature of artistic discourse are consistently examined in global linguistics. Linguistic centers worldwide are increasingly focused on the challenge of reconstructing the linguistic landscape of the world, along with the methods by which communicants perceive and articulate this landscape. Artistic discourse, in particular, mirrors not only the worldview of a nation but also the mental states and individual perspectives of authors and characters. Consequently, there is a growing urgency to enhance the methods of analyzing discursive activities specific to art, the means of expressing content, and their direct implementation.

The reforms carried out in our country, along with modern linguistics, play an important role in expanding the scope of intercultural communication. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev stated, "Science and enlightenment are important in increasing the intellectual and spiritual capabilities of not only young people, but also our entire society." Therefore, scientific research is one of the main sources of the country's development, and the field of linguistics is no exception.

One significant reason speakers often indirectly express pragmatic goals in speech communication is to adhere to the rules of politeness. To show politeness to the listener and maintain their respect, speakers employ linguistic strategies that align with their own mentality and social status. Researchers, seeking to explain the pervasive use of the concept of "politeness" within pragmatics, emphasize that language practice should serve as a means to preserve the interlocutor's identity, including their status and image within the community [Vershuren 1999:45]. According to the theory of adaptation, polite adaptation involves interlocutors selecting contextually appropriate strategies to clearly and effectively convey their thoughts, thus fulfilling the communicative need.

The concept of "manner/treatment" has its origins in ancient Egypt and India, with significant development during antiquity. In ancient times, interpersonal relations were intertwined with philosophical perspectives, forming a comprehensive system. Democritus, for instance, perceived philosophy as an art of living, encompassing good speech and behavior. Socrates and Plato viewed philosophy as an equal dialogue, a mutual conversation that involves understanding oneself and others, as well as grasping the truth. Aristotle was the first to use the term "manner/treatment," laying the foundation for the system of art and culture. This term encompasses a complex process of activity involving cooperative strategies for exchanging information, understanding, and perceiving others. The focus of this concept is an ideal spiritual reality, encompassing the mental, emotional, and voluntary aspects of human thought and consciousness. Its subject matter includes the spiritual and moral dimensions of behavior and activity, as well as the specific mental processes of groups engaged in various tasks. Psychological sciences, such as communication psychology, behavioral psychology, and personality psychology, provide clear guidelines for different forms of behavior and spiritual communication, highlighting their mutual influence. Consequently, as a social category, manner/treatment permeates all areas of life. It is crucial to emphasize that speech etiquette plays a significant role in communication, from informal to formal contexts, across all life situations.

Literature analysis

In recent years, the linguistic structure and pragmatic features of the text have been studied by a number of foreign linguists. Uzbek linguists are also conducting research in this direction. In the works of scientists such as V. Humboldt, D. Oswell, A. Duranti, N. F. Alefirenko, V. I. Karasik, S. Muminov, communication etiquette, its national-cultural features, social-cultural aspects were studied. The principle of politeness was described by P. Brown and S. Levinson in a slightly different way [3; 114, 6; 45, 8; 78, 4; 59].

Research methodology

According to the linguistic dictionary, speech etiquette represents a system of stable speech formulas established by society in order to maintain communication in a tone selected according to social roles and role positions in relation to each other. Uzbek also has national-cultural characteristics of speech etiquette. Etiquette formulas are connected with people's lifestyle and national traditions. Turkish and Uzbek cultures have some similarities due to their cultural, religious and linguistic backgrounds, while English or British cultures differ in this respect and appear to be more modernized or westernized. For example, in Uzbek culture, a kiss on the face among intimate women is a sign of affection, gentleness, and respect. However, there is a taboo in social places among the wider members of society. Because it is highly related to the observance of religious rules among the members of the society. In Uzbek culture, they may use a handshake or a hug when greeting or introducing each other. In Uzbek culture, women and men do not usually shake hands with each other, unless the woman shakes the man's hand first. Therefore, it can be seen that there is a cultural gap at the behavioral level in all these cultures. There is also a pragmatic gap in the use of language in these cultures, which will be analyzed below. Forms of address have other important social functions, such as showing respect, showing intimacy, honoring, or denigrating other people. In the next part, we will mainly discuss the use of forms of address in some specific social settings. In Uzbek culture, politeness plays an important role in interaction, and it has been a long tradition that respecting both the young and the elderly is the key to establishing strong social ties with each other. As in the Uzbek and English culture, there is a special appeal to relatives in the family. Children usually address their parents as *dada*, *dadajon*, *oyi*, *oyijon*. During the conversation, addresses such as *o'g'lim*-my son, *singlim*-sister, *ukajon*-brother, *akajon*-brother are also used. *Beloved*, *dear*, *my beloved*, *my baby* (children) are often used to refer to beloved spouses. In some cases of address, giving someone's name is used not only to draw the listener's attention to the speaker, but also to express gratitude. Such methods of address are expressed by words, expressions of gratitude, specific means of expressing gratitude or substantive adjectives expressing the meaning of gratitude: "Assalom aleykum hurmatli Ra'no Yusupova", "Xayrli tong, Janobi Oliylari". Addressing functions that can express respect and gratitude. Such methods of address are usually used when addressing high-ranking, respected people, foreigners, and in such cases it is expressed using specific words or morphemes: *hurmatli*, *xonimlar*, *janoblar*, *azizim*, *hazratlari* /*Janobi oliylari*, *azizlar*, *janoblar*, *bekalar*, *xonimlar* etc. Even these features are available in other languages; they have no exact equivalents in English.

Although this tradition is losing its cultural value these days, there are still people who use this expression, and now it is fashionable to call wives *oyisi*- "bolasining onasi" and *dadasi*- "bolasining otasi". The Uzbek language has a collection of expressions used to greet people, such as "xush kelibsiz". Answer: *Xush ko'rdik* means "I'm glad to see you here". The word "Salom" in Uzbek is used to greet young people, regardless of age and time. There are also certain ways of apologizing or getting attention, and these differ in different cultures. For example, "Kechirasiz" is "excuse me" in Uzbek and is used to get someone's attention or ask to go somewhere. For example, in Uzbek culture, the word *sorry* is used to apologize or make a mistake. English people use the word "sorry" very often and it has many reasons and meanings, making it a popular English word for English people or other non-natives living in the UK.

Uzbeks use the word "Yoqimli ishtaha" while eating to say "Enjoy your meal" to someone, and end the good words with "omin" when the elder or male member of the family wishes. The word "Rahmat" is often used as "Thank you" where a person wants to thank someone. English people also have a lot of ways to say "Thank you", "Thank you very much", "I'm grateful" if they want to express their gratitude to the recipient, and the situations vary depending on the context. The most remarkable phenomenon in this regard is that in the Uzbek language, when helping the elderly, they wish a lot of good words to the person who helped them, saying "omin" to express their gratitude. For example, in the Uzbek language, "Umringiz uzoq bo'lsin" means "May your life be long", while English people say such wishes on special events of the people, for example, on birthdays. In addition, there are certain words and expressions that belong only to a certain culture. For example, Uzbeks use the

word "Labbay" when someone calls or when they have not heard and want to be repeated by the addressee. Originally, this word was derived from the Arabic phrase "Labbay", which translates as "I am here". There is no equivalent of this word in English.

Pragmatic perspectives on the analysis of communication principles and speech act theory have undoubtedly facilitated the description and explanation of how speech structures convey implicit meaning. Applying these theories enables the differentiation between pragmatic content and referential meaning, as well as the identification of the speaker's intended purpose in using specific linguistic means. Researchers frequently reference the "Cooperative Principle" proposed by H. Grice to describe instances of implied expression.

J. Leach notes in his book "Principles of Pragmatics" that the principle of cooperation helps to form the relationship between content and illocutionary force [10; 148]. But this principle is not sufficient to explain why speakers express their intentions so indirectly. Because the principle of cooperation relies more on proposition. That is why the politeness principle proposed by J. Leach relies on pragmatic rules that have a social and spiritual direction. A scientist who considers pragmatic rules to be an integral part of the principle of cooperation uses the following example to describe the relationship of these phenomena:

Linda: We'll all miss Jill and Chris.

Lucy: Well, we all miss Jill.

Lucy is apparently not following the quantity rule here. Because when Linda asks to confirm her opinion, Lucy only confirms part of it and denies the rest. The implication is that Lucy thinks they don't miss Chris. But it is natural to ask how this implicature appears. Lucy should actually speak the truth clearly and without digressing on the principle of cooperation, but she does not do so in order to maintain a polite attitude. The principle of politeness is described by J. Leach as follows:

- 1) Use disrespectful phrases as little as possible;
- 2) Use polite sentences more [10; 260].

Thus, the principle of politeness requires respect for the identity of another person, his independence and location in space. We avoid impacting into the lives of others and judging their activities unfairly. We show people that we like their company and that we are happy about their success. This type of politeness includes qualities such as agreeableness, kindness, humility, and sympathy. At the same time, too much respect indicates the social distance between the interlocutors and causes the activation of the sarcastic strategy. Non-compliance with the principle of respect is more often observed in the communication of close people and young people.

The principle of politeness was described by P. Brown and S. Levinson in a slightly different way [3; 115]. According to their theory, people need to be approved by others to maintain their "o'zligi" (faces). Scientists note that the concept of "face" has two forms:

- 1) Negative face: the right to freedom of action and freedom from imposition;
- 2) Positive face: the need to be appreciated by others and to maintain a positive selfimage.

In daily communication, participants typically adhere to the principle of politeness. A face-threatening act occurs when a speaker performs a speech act that undermines another person's respect, compelling interlocutors to seek ways to mitigate this impact. However, as noted by pragmalinguists, avoiding such situations is challenging [3; 145]. For instance, when a speaker performs an act of showing favor, it can appear self-deprecating. Additionally, reminding a listener to perform a task can threaten their identity, implying doubt about their memory and undermining their independence. Consequently, natural communication often involves threats to identity. Interlocutors must adhere to the principle of cooperation and employ politeness strategies to achieve their communicative goals. According to P. Brown and his co-author, at least five strategies should be employed to mitigate the risk of identity threat. These strategies include both overt and implicit expressions of respect, as well as positive and negative politeness.

Politeness should align with the psychological landscape of the speaker. Personal attributes, such as mental state, desires, and interests, as well as broader factors like worldview, cultural knowledge, and experiences, influence one's communicative behavior. Given the complexity of these factors, speakers cannot simultaneously employ them all to resolve communication challenges;

instead, they must select the most advantageous ones. Speakers adopt a balanced communication strategy, considering the psychological landscape of the listener, including their psyche, character, and desires, to achieve effective communication outcomes. Similarly, listeners also engage in such adaptive actions. Understanding the conversational meaning necessitates adapting to the speaker's psychological world. Thus, adaptation theory frames politeness as a phenomenon inherent in the process of linguistic expression. The speaker's attitude towards the listener is evident in their implementation of politeness strategies. Although politeness theory primarily examines direct oral communication, its application to the analysis of dialogic interactions among characters in artistic works presents minimal difficulty. Writers employ various politeness strategies to delineate character relationships. Consequently, using polite strategies does not invariably lead to goal attainment; at times, speakers may achieve their objectives through more direct means. Nevertheless, politeness invariably influences the morale and behavior of interlocutors. Hence, to effectively engender politeness, it is prudent to select strategies that resonate with the interlocutors' psychological realms. Failure to consider the situational context when employing politeness strategies may result in communication that appears inappropriate, rude, or excessively polite.

The characters use politeness as a communicative strategy to adapt to the material, social and mental worlds. The material world reflects when and where the dialogue takes place. This world is essentially a natural environment in which communication takes place. A material context can be a workplace, a home, or a community. The role of the speaker in the material world is important in the emergence of linguistic choice and meaning. Indicators of language use are clearly manifested when changes related to material conditions occur. The indicators of time and space have a direct impact on the choice of language tools and the effectiveness of the principle of politeness in the surrounding environment. For example, if we take the time indicator, saying "Xayrli tong-Good morning" to someone who wakes up around noon is more a sign of irony than a sign of respect. Complimenting a person's nice clothes can be an example of politeness, but you should avoid such compliments for someone who is wearing a veil and choose a different politeness strategy. All of these are material factors that influence language choice.

Conclusion

In summary, employing a polite strategy is not always synonymous with achieving the intended goal, as speakers may sometimes attain their objectives through more direct means. Nevertheless, irrespective of the approach, politeness exerts a significant influence on the morale and engagement of interlocutors. Consequently, to effectively cultivate a sense of politeness, it is advisable to select strategies that resonate with the psychological realms of the interlocutors. When language users align their politeness strategies with the situational context, the desired communication outcomes can be achieved. However, failure to consider the context may result in speech acts that appear inappropriate, rude, or excessively polite. One of the primary motivations for a speaker to express pragmatic goals directly or indirectly in communication is to adhere to the norms of politeness. In order to demonstrate politeness towards the interlocutor and uphold their respect, individuals endeavor to utilize linguistic tools that resonate with the interlocutor's mentality and societal standing. In accordance with the theory of adaptation, polite adaptation refers to the interlocutors' deliberate selection of appropriate strategies to effectively articulate their viewpoints, thereby fulfilling the communicative imperative. Within adaptation theory, politeness is construed as a phenomenon that emerges during the process of linguistic expression. The speaker's disposition towards the listener is manifested in the execution of politeness strategies. Employing this principle yields significant insights when analyzing the dialogic interactions among characters in artistic works. Authors employ diverse polite strategies to delineate character relationships, underscoring the efficacy of this principle in literary analysis.

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